

Gezi - 10 Years After, Maxim Gorki Theatre, 26 May - 25 June, 2023

Gezinema World Cinema Documentaries

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Co-curated by Şirin Fulya Erensoy and Necati Sönmez

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Screening: Audience Emancipated: The Struggle for the Emek Movie Theatre, Emek Bizim İstanbul Bizim Initiative, 2016 and Love is Over, Mert Kaya, 2017

Audience Emancipated chronicles one of the most prominent struggles that took place in the heart of Istanbul and paved the way for the Gezi Resistance. It tells of the struggle around the Emek Theatre, which was demolished against the people's consent and their common good, and turned into a shopping mall, through the eyes of the activists and spectators. The film consists of footage which people who joined the struggle collected, and in this sense, aims to reflect the common imagination of the people who defended their right to the city. It carries the idea of the new public spirit that gained visibility with the Gezi Resistance through political mobilisation onto the cinema screen.

Acabou o Amor is named after a slogan chanted during Brazil's uprisings in 2013: 'Love is over! This is Turkey now!' After participating in the Gezi uprising, Mert Kaya travels to Brazil in pursuit of questions raised during his own experiences. On the 10th anniversary of Gezi, we come together to contemplate two parallel uprisings in Turkey and Brazil, while stopping by other struggles; from Tunisia to Egypt, Spain to Greece, these are places joined in solidarity against neoliberal politics, each rising up to claim their 'right to the city'.

Q&A Session with Senem Aytaç and Mert Kaya, moderated by Şirin Fulya Erensoy and Necati Sönmez

Emek Bizim İstanbul Bizim (Emek is Ours İstanbul is Ours) is an initiative that was formed in 2010 to organise demonstrations and events against the demolition of the Emek Movie Theater in Beyoğlu, İstanbul. Since 2013, the initiative has collected video and sound recordings of the demonstrations made by activists and various filmmakers, which then turned into the documentary *Audience Emancipated: The Struggle for the Emek Movie Theater*.

Mert Kaya is a documentary filmmaker and video artist based in İstanbul. His interest in cinema derives from the motivation to discuss social issues with a visual medium. His debut film *Acabou o Amor* (2017) was screened in various film festivals. He collaborated as a video artist in the project *Side by Side* exhibited in the Venice Biennale 2021. He is currently working on a documentary about Anadolu Kültür and its 20 years of resilient actions in civil society in Turkey.

ŞE: Before we open this session, Senem Aytaç has a few words to share.

SA: I would like to mention the Gezi prisoners here, because especially Can Atalay and Mücella Yapıcı were one of the most prominent figures in our struggle for the Emek Movie Theatre, and as you know, they are still in prison and we do not know how long it will take. At least I'm glad to have them here with their voices and their opinions. As we have seen in the film, there were a lot of struggles going on during our fight for the Emek Movie Theatre, for instance, there was a huge urban transformation project going on at Tarlabası. People's houses were being demolished and being transferred to the outskirts of the city, but there was no strong opposition towards this. There were small organisations who were fighting for the cause. There were things going on at the Gezi park as well, in connection with this group, so we were standing side by side, and trying to raise awareness at Gezi as well, but that did not happen. But then when the theatre struggle began, we were also surprised

that so many people joined us. That is why we tried to build a discourse to gather all sorts of - not only in Beyoğlu - problems related to the city... I think the discourse around Emek Sineması spoke directly to people's personal memories and had the advantage to be symbolic. Right after that the struggle came that of the Gezi park protests but it was actually weird because we actually lost our struggle... But we just moved on with Gezi.

NS: The struggle for the Emek Movie Theatre was also the starting point of slogans which became a fundamental part of the discourse during the Gezi Park Protests as well....

SA: We had a meeting for the organisation of one of the demonstrations. Two of our friends joined and said: last night we watched a documentary from 1968 and there was this slogan and we translated trying to find a rhythm to it, and suddenly we came up with the slogan: Bu Daha Başlangıç, Mücadeleye Devam (This Is Only The Beginning, Continue The Fight) and we thought: wow. From that particular moment, it spread, just like: Emek Bizim, İstanbul Bizim (Emek Is Ours, İstanbul Is Ours), and I think slogans link struggles one to another, they travel throughout the world from one country to another, from one time to another. I actually find it quite poetic. For instance, after the first police attack before Gezi in April... Everybody started shouting at once: Faşizme Karşı Omuz Omuz (Shoulder to Shoulder Against Fascism). Most of the crowd did not even know this slogan but it gained momentum. I feel like the ghosts or the souls of struggles travel through slogans.

ŞE: Speaking of slogans, Turkey is linked to Brazil through a slogan. I really appreciate your film, Mert, and how you link your personal story both of being in Brazil and being in Gezi, and visiting Brazil after the Gezi park protests and after their protests as well. The film reminds me of another film we will be screening next week: Love Will Change The Earth, which also takes part in Gezi and talks to the different protagonists of the protests. You do the same for the case of Brazil; you speak to all these different protagonists, and I love the fact that they highlight what unites them despite the extensive effort of polarisation in society, the class differences, and so forth; they talk about what unites them and the fact that it's a leaderless protest very much just like Gezi. Although again, despite the efforts of the government trying to pinpoint it and criminalising certain people as those leaders. Can you tell us how when you went back to Brazil and how you decided to create this landscape of leaderless protestors in order to talk about what had happened during the actual protests of 2013?

MK: Actually while I'm watching the two films together now - The Struggle for the Emek Movie Theatre and Love is Over, which I had watched separately before - it was quite interesting because the first film is made by a collective and about the memory of the Emek Theatre movement, and my film was mostly driven by my personal story. But these protests took place in a space where personal and collective stories intersect. Many of the characters in my film were friends from when I lived in Brazil in 2011, a year before the Gezi protests. I also felt this when I first screened the film in Brazil in 2019, because the story that was personal for me was actually part of a collective one for them. In fact, the reason why I made the film about the story in Brazil is that I cannot distance myself from the images of the protests I was part of. For instance, it was difficult for me to watch the movie about Emek, because the footage is quite harsh. I could not make anything out of it. There are many images from these movements. I could not look back at Gezi. So to look at my own history and our recent history of struggles, I choose to speak to my Brazilian friends and make the relation through them.

ŞE: As we were speaking about images, I was interested in the way you put your images together, Senem. There was a pool of images for which you made an open call, and aside from these images, there are creative links that you make to certain films, historical moments and struggles demonstrated in those films. Can you talk about that editing process, how you used those images from the pool, and why you wanted to link it creatively to those other particular times and places globally?

SA: Sure. First I should talk a bit about the production process of the film because we did not know that we were going to make a film at the beginning. We did not have the intention, we were waiting for someone to make a film about the struggle, but that never happened. So we decided to make it ourselves. After Gezi, we made a call: there is a bar called Muaf where we were always meeting up in Beyoğlu and we asked for people who had footage in their cameras, phones etc. to bring them to us so we could collect them all. Our only intention then was to collect images and footage of the struggle at Emek so that people can use this and produce their own films. We were speaking about how one could technically and logistically produce a collective film, we were discussing it, but we actually wanted to gather the material and open the pool. As the political oppression became harsher and we were not able to be out on the streets and people were feeling depressed around 2015, we decided to use this period to reflect on what we did. One of our points of discussion was “how to lose” - ways of losing, politically - we decided to go through the material and make a film out of it, and one of our friends, Fırat Yücel, was also wanting to learn film editing, so he took the material and played with it. He sent us a brief, very messy but beautiful draft, and Zeyno Pekünlü, who is also a video artist, worked on it. Using everyone’s material, we decided we were not going to use any extra material coming from outside the pool... We would only use the material of the people in the struggle because we were also thinking theoretically, like we are demonstrating the revolution of the theatre, and the audience is the demonstrator now, so who is the producer... Audience emancipation: we were trying to blur the lines between being an audience and an active protester... So it made sense to use the material of the people who were demonstrating. However, of course, some of us are film critics and could not help ourselves to tie it to film history. Of course, our political and filmic imagination and understanding goes in parallel. Actually one of the first screenings we had during the demonstrations was Dziga Vertov’s *Man with a Movie Camera*, so we decided to start with that, to start a tradition. Then we decided to use Costa-Gravas films, as he also participated in the struggle, so it was also an organic tie. We use that particular sequence like that, where the police attacks, since at the time we were being objected to too much police violence and did not want to repeat that violence for the audience and distract it cinematically - to understand it but not feel it as much that is why we made that cinematic estrangement.

NS: The most impressive part is when you use the old fragment of İstanbul Film Festival which is one of the main organisations which used Emek. But they failed to protect the theatre. The annual film festival had to move from Beyoğlu after an incident.

SA: They closed the theatre silently. When it was time for Film Ekimi (in October) there weren’t any announcements. When the film festival was to open in April, nobody was talking about it. The first protest in the opening ceremony gave voice to the closing down of the theatre... This

continued for years... They were accomplices to the struggle, but of course they were playing their game to protect their own institution. The struggle had too many faces, there were civil rights activists, urban planners, architects, film critics, cinephiles, anarchists, etc., so there was a very weird combination of people coming together. I remember, I was a board member of the Film Critics Association back then and also an activist, so I was changing hats all the time... There were press releases we wrote as the association that were different to the ones we wrote as people on the streets. It was very advantageous for us to move between different roles. Famous people were also raising their voices, cultural institutions of course had their own interests. But we were also squatting the place. And of course the cultural institutions were always changing their position according to the toughening of the actions.

NS: ... We witness the reclaiming of spaces... In Emek, Gezi Park, Brazil... Do you think there is a constant struggle for the reclaiming of spaces be it a cinema, or a theatre, or a park, or square?

MK: Actually, from 2010 until 2013, we witnessed this... In Istanbul... It is not a surprise that the struggle over Emek was opening up a way to the Gezi protests. The same slogans were used in both movements. In the case of Brazil, we see the same. Many people in the film for instance, are not from this particular movement, but they found many reasons to protest - the right to the city, housing problems linked to it, etc. This is a common ground for that period of time in the movements around the world.

SA: I think the city as a commodity is a common ground. The advantage with the Emek theatre was that it was not owned by private property. That is why we could strongly claim it because there were many other theatres that were demolished in Beyoğlu, and many other shops and places, but Emek was owned by the state, therefore it was public. We were trying to make people aware that public spaces are actually owned by the public and we have a right to say something, to decide its fate. Around the world, during the 2000s, there were many cases of regaining the city and seeing the city as a place that we live in rather than a commodity in itself. Not only in Brazil, but many other places, this happened and will continue happening...

MK: Now that we are looking back, back then our discussion was around a realisation of the city and the public, and now 10 years after as a retrospective, we can see that while we are living under rising authoritarianism all over the world - Brazil is another example - we now see that we are losing basic rights.

ŞE: Any questions from the audience?

Q: Thank you for your films. The ways in which the rights to the city are deeply linked with other rights that are currently and have been under threat for the last decade or two in the case of Turkey, and with the rising fascism all over the world right now. I wondered about the realisation

that you were critiquing at that point is also deeply tied to the rise of fascism or fascistic forms of authoritarianism that we are experiencing and when watching your films, I could not help but feel sad, because the feeling that we were accomplishing something and much was accomplished has been replaced by fear and some level of hopelessness... We are approaching the second round of elections (in Turkey); but during the first round we know what happened, so... Change is not necessarily going to come from the spirit of electoral politics. Technically, how can we use urban movements today do you think in a way that disrupts the new formations of power that we are experiencing? Thank you guys.

SA: I do not know the exact answer. The only thing that can save us is to think from a historical perspective. That gives me relief when I pretend to remind myself that we are never at the highest point in history and I remember how I felt before Gezi, when I was really depressed, during Roboski for instance. I felt like: horrible things are happening, and nothing is going to change and then Gezi happened and this shocked many of us. Of course we never know. Maybe that is a good thing. How history surprises us with new things. I know now we are at a low point... You do not know what will ignite something... We have to try and push every button, however small... When I force myself to speak in a hopeful way, this is what I can say.

MK: We are passing through very difficult times. Still I believe that memory brings hope and amnesia brings despair. Hope is not a blind optimism but we never forget and the ones who are in power never make us forget their accomplishments. Even though you were saying that we lost the Emek struggle, what we saw on the screen most of the time were the moments of struggle, resistance, moments of being able to be together... Depends on the lens... Remembering that moment after 10 years... At the time we said, things might change in 5 or in 10 years... And now, we can say it changed but... Remembering brings hope.

SA: It is not about the political situation, but I was screening the film like a year ago in Paris. There was a protest to save a theatre there - La Clef. It was really successful at first - they squatted the cinema..., opened a cooperative, and when they were squatting they also screened our film there. When I met them later, the guy said he joined the struggle after he watched our film thinking: Oh my God, we cannot lose it this way... and they won. So I find it very metaphorically beautiful that our loss was someone else's inspiration to join a struggle. Life happens in mysterious ways.

ŞE: My feeling when I watch these films is that if it happened once, it can happen again.

Q: Thank you. It is quite empowering to see them both together which makes a different film. I really cried during the one on Emek and now I feel a strange joy that it is over. I wanted to ask Senem, looking back after 10 years, can you give a self-criticism of the initiative. Now you're here and looking back, what are your views of the initiative?

SA: Actually the first initiative was called Istanbul Kültür Sanat Varyetesi, which started the first protests in the theatre and the opening of the film festival. The initiative itself changed over the course of four years and we had inner conflicts. The experience itself is very valuable. None of us knew how a horizontal organisation would work, the relationships, etc... It was a valuable experience because the environment was changing all the time. When I say “we”: the “we” is an empty signifier. Many people left, then came back, changed their perspective, etc. That’s why I think it is difficult to speak about this as a whole unified initiative. So that is partially hard to criticise too. The crew that put this film together is a small part of it. When I screened this film at another theatre, this time during a theatre struggle in Belgrade, and their film was only about the inner struggles of the organisation - they won the struggle but they made a film about how awful the political discussions amongst them were - the Trotskists, the syndicates, the freelance directors were always fighting with each other, so when you watch the film it seems like it’s impossible but then they won. It is called *Occupied Cinema* by Senka Domanović. This could have been another way to make a film but we chose not to do that.

MK: When I went to Brazil to shoot this film, my intention was to discuss how social movements must organise themselves. Most of my questions were about that. After Gezi, horizontal and autonomous organisations were points we were discussing, and during Emek. Maybe that was your reason for your film... When I finished the film, it was 2017, we were living under different conditions, it became a movie about remembering those days. Our discussions were removed at that point.

ŞE: After Gezi there were a lot of social movements or groups that became more visible or strengthened their alliances and started to have more presence in the public. Here I am thinking of the LGBTQI+ movement, the women’s movement, they obviously existed before, but they gained much more visibility. Is there a similar kind of link with Brazil? I think the student movement is quite prominent and has a very long history dating way before 2013. Since that time and keeping in mind your links to your friends or activist colleagues, has there been this kind of visibility that has appeared in the more public sphere?

MK: Actually in my view, as you said in Turkey, these social movements came first and many of organisations that were linked to the “older” ways of doing politics were demolished in a way. Many organisations were separated, etc. In the case of Brazil as well; there was a high schools movement which was massive and gained force from the protests in 2013 and these discussions of how to make politics horizontal in Brazil also demolished organisations, and it’s also strange that after 10 years, we are stuck in electoral politics...

NS: There is a film on student politics in Brazil called *Your Turn*, that we will screen on the 4th of June.

Q: In the last couple of years, in the cultural sector and in the cinema, making films has come under pressure... There are new tactics of censorship... How do you see the current situation - of course this also depends on tomorrow's election - how do you see the new future?

MK: You are right. Even in small, independent circles, it is becoming difficult to make films. It is impossible to find any financial support from the state. We had the: Yeni Film Fonu (New Film Fund) that you can see at the beginning of the film on Emek, which is a fund to support documentaries and founded by Osman Kavala... the Anatolian Cultural Centre... Osman Kavala is in prison, Çiğdem Mater is also in prison... It is getting more and more difficult to make films from "the outside". Actually even thinking of making films is getting difficult and I am forcing myself - my personal story - to be able to think about films and express myself with it in the conditions that we are living under.

ŞE: Thinking about making films is becoming difficult is an important point you are making...as Çiğdem Mater is in prison for a film she did not even make...Senem you were saying something regarding the documentation itself, that no one was making a film about your struggle, so you decided to make it yourselves. You documented that collective struggle because if you are not going to do it then the media is going to be talking the narrative in a completely different direction so the protagonists of the struggle will not be able to have their words spread. Documentation then turns into a collective way of filmmaking as you were talking about. I think this is something important to keep doing in one way or another and then see how that can transform into maybe a more cohesive narrative.

SA: I was involved with the film magazine called Altyazı which was published for 20 years but now is completely digital. We were publishing the magazine out of Bosphorus University and one of the first things that the first appointed rector did was to cut our funding and throw us out of the university. We were also very active in the political field of film, objecting to censorship as well, so we founded an association and on our own founded a new outlet called Altyazı Fasikül, just to be able to record what is happening right now. The only aim we had was: people are not even talking about the censorship cases anymore because they are afraid, so we are trying to open up a space where we can at least tell stories about their censorship. Sometimes we do not publish it and keep it to ourselves so that years later, they are at least archived in a way to keep a record of history.

Q: Thank you for these films. Being here has awakened many emotions in me because I am also from Turkey and it still hurts to see some moments I remember and feel... My question is for Senem: what kind of knowledge preparation is transferred and transformed from Emek to Gezi from an organisational point of view and from your personal experience and observations?

SA: There was not only Emek, but also Pride and an Internet censorship case at that time, where there was a great march against that as well. I think there was a brief moment where people outside the usual leftist circles were out on the street struggling for their rights which was directly related with their lives. I think there was a new crowd that started to feel the need to be out on the streets as present bodies to shout out

because they felt like they were not being heard, many things were touching their lives. I think Gezi was partially like this as well. For a very long period of time, there was no police violence towards demonstrations, and people were becoming more and more courageous. We are not used to that in Turkey because demonstrations are usually equal to police violence. For a brief period for some particular demonstrations, that was not the case so we were able to be playful, creative and had the space where people feel safe and rightful to be there, and not afraid. I think that weaved the path to Gezi in that sense, with the slogans, the particular kinds of concerts, film screenings, different ways of protesting not just shouting the usual slogans, but trying to be more/open a more creative, artistic space. Take it from Occupy, throughout the 90s there is this new wave of protest culture... Partially there's one cornerstone there.

NS: There were a lot of famous public figures in your film . actors, filmmakers and the police know them now.

SA: I was afraid that ... they were going to be hurt... They were in front of the police barricades... That was also a turning point. People were really shocked when the police did attack. They could not make sense of it. Many of them probably faced police violence for the first time in their lives. Therefore, I think... anger also arose during the Gezi park protests.

ŞE: Thank you very much Mert and Senem for being with us.

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